

FUZZY LOGIC MODEL FOR SENSORY EVALUATION OF CONVECTIVE AND MICROWAVE DRIED READY-TO-EAT (RTE) PEARL MILLET STICKS

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Abstract

Ready-to-eat (RTE) Pearl Millet sticks were prepared from cooked dough of pearl millet grits with other ingredients by drying with convective and microwave drying. Three different samples viz. pearl millet sticks with onion slices (S1), pearl millet sticks (S2) and market product (S3) were prepared and evaluated for their liking by a panel of twenty judges using fuzzy logic technique. Ranking of the three samples was carried out on the basis of their quality attributes like Color, flavour, taste, and mouthfeel. The judges' responses were obtained in terms of poor, fair, medium, good, and excellent, and were used as mathematical variables in the development of fuzzy logic mathematical models. The output of fuzzy logic models was determined using the concept of triplets, overall sensory scores, membership function on a standard fuzzy scale, and similarity values to rank the samples and determine the relative importance of quality attributes of the samples. The results revealed that Sample (S2) was rated as 'Very Good' followed by Sample (S1) as 'Very Good' and Sample (S3) as 'Medium'. The Mouthfeel or texture and taste were the highest quality attributes for pearl millet sticks while flavour was the weakest among the quality attributes. The findings of the fuzzy logic analysis as well as the judges' opinions on general quality attributes indicated that the Fuzzy logic technique can be applied to analyze the sensory data for the ranking of the millet stick samples and quality attributes.

Keywords: Microwave drying, Pearl millet sticks, Fuzzy scale, Color, Flavour, Texture

Introduction

Sensory evaluation is a collection of procedures for accurately measuring human responses to foods, with the goal of reducing the potentially biasing effects of brand identification and other information on customer perception. Traditional techniques for sensory evaluation of food products generally employed for the sensory evaluation only in a qualitative sense and cannot perform a precise quantitative assessment (Vivek *et al.*, 2019). The collected sensory evaluation data of products have been evaluated using different statistical methods. The computational processes using statistical and factorial analyses, on the other hand, are ineffective because uncertainties in these cases have a non-probabilistic character due to the imprecision of the means (Martnez 2007). So the novel techniques such as fuzzy set theory have been effectively used in assessing the sensory characteristics of various traditional as well as novel food products developed through fortification and modified processing techniques.

Fuzzy sets theory was proposed by Zadeh (1965), which allows for the mathematical treatment of uncertain phenomena. Chen *et al.* (1988) established a model for sensory data analysis. Zhang and Litchfield (1991) proposed a fuzzy comprehensive model for food ranking and the development of new food products. Fuzzy logic is a useful technique for analysing vague and imprecise data and drawing important conclusions about food acceptance, rejection, ranking, and strong and weak qualities (Shinde and Pardeshi, 2014). Linguistic variables (e.g., not satisfactory, good, outstanding, etc.) are used in fuzzy modelling to develop relationships between independent (e.g., colour, aroma, taste, mouthfeel, convenience, etc.) and dependent (e.g., acceptance, rejection, ranking, strong and weak food attributes) variables (Das, 2005; Routray and Mishra, 2011). Unlike the nine-point hedonic scale (BIS, 1971), judges' linguistic responses can be translated into numerical values for comparison using fuzzy analysis. Instead of using average scores to compare the attributes of a sample, fuzzy sets can be used to analyse sensory data (Lincklaen *et al.*, 1989; Kavdir and Gayer, 2003).

Food samples and their quality attributes are ranked using triplets associated with sensory scales, triplets for sensory score, triplets for sensory score of quality attributes, triplets for relative weightage of quality attributes, triplets for overall sensory score, values of membership function of standard fuzzy scale, values of overall membership function of sensory scores on standard fuzzy scale, and triplets for overall sensory score.

This method has been successfully applied for mango drinks (Jaya and Das, 2003), dahi (curd) powder (Routray and Mishra, 2011), instant green tea powder (Sinija and Mishra, 2011), pineapple rasgulla (Sarkar

et al., 2020), microwave assisted ultrasound treated soymilk beverage (Kumar *et al.*, 2021), soy paneer (Uprit and Mishra, 2002) and Kharodi chunks (Solanke *et al.*, 2019). Very few researchers have applied fuzzy logic for sensory analysis of RTE dried snack foods. As a result, in the current investigation, a sensory analysis using fuzzy logic was attempted to assess the acceptability of Pearl millet sticks samples.

Materials and Method**Preparation of product samples and sensory evaluation**

Pearl millet sticks is a RTE traditional snack food prepared from cooked dough of pearl millet grits with other ingredients like oil, garlic, ginger, chili powder, salt, etc. and subsequently cold extruded in the form of sticks using hand operated extruder. Extruded sticks were partially dried using convective hot air at 120 C for 20 min for imparting case hardening. The case-hardened sticks were further dried in microwave oven at optimal levels of microwave power (540 W) and microwave drying time (17 min). Three test samples (S1, S2 and S3) were prepared for sensory evaluation. Two samples were prepared from optimally microwave dried product viz. pearl millet sticks with onion slices (S1) and pearl millet sticks (S2). The market product (Kharodi chunks) was taken as control (S3) for comparison with prepared product. A panel of twenty judges evaluated the sensory characteristics of the test samples and the judge's responses were calculated in terms of numerical values.

The panel of judges including ten males and ten females in the age range of 20 to 50 years (Ranganna, 1987; Singh *et al.*, 2012) from the department's faculty and research scholars were selected based on good health, average sensitivity, sensory evaluation interests, and familiarity with snack foods. The data obtained from subjective evaluation of three test samples were analyzed by using fuzzy logic. The panelists were asked to rank their preferences for each sample based on the colour, flavour, taste, and mouthfeel (texture) quality attributes. As the crispness of product is perceived through a combination of tactile, kinesthetic, auditory sensations (Heidenreich *et al.*, 2004) and also associated with rapid drop of force during mastication process (Vincent, 1998), texture of the test samples was tested in terms of mouthfeel. Before the sensory evaluation, the judges were informed with the definitions of the qualitative features of RTE snack food. They were asked to take two or three samples before tasting them and to provide a flavour score first on the score sheet. They were also advised to rinse their mouth with lukewarm water in between two successive samples (Das, 2005; Sinija and Mishra, 2011).

After tasting the sample, judges were instructed to place a tick mark next to the appropriate fuzzy scale factor for each of the quality

attributes. The samples were rated as “Not satisfactory”, “Fair”, “Medium”, “Good” and “Excellent”. The judges were also instructed to rank the qualitative characteristics of the samples in general (Shinde *et al.*, 2016) by giving tickmark to the respective scale factors, viz. “Not at all important”, “Somewhat important”, “Important”, “Highly important” and “Extremely important”. The set of observations were analysed by using Fuzzy analysis of sensory scores.

Fuzzy modelling of sensory data

The following are the key steps in the fuzzy modelling of sensory evaluation which are

(1) calculation of overall sensory scores of the samples in the form of triplets (Fig. 1); (2) estimation of membership function on standard fuzzy scale (Fig. 2); (3) computation of overall membership function on standard fuzzy scale (Fig. 3); (4) estimation of similarity values and ranking of the samples; and (5) quality attribute ranking of the samples in general. All of the following stages were calculated using a programming code in the MATLAB 7.0 software (Das, 2005; McGarrity, 2008).

Triplets associated with five-point sensory scale

On a five-point scale, the sensory ratings were converted into a set of three numbers called a ‘triplet’ which is used to represent triangular membership function distribution pattern of sensory scales. The

$$CS1 = \frac{0(0 \ 0 \ 25)+4(25 \ 25 \ 25)+6(50 \ 25 \ 25)+8(75 \ 25 \ 25)+2(100 \ 25 \ 0)}{20} \dots 1$$

Triplets for each quality attribute of all the samples and quality attributes of the samples in general were obtained as per eq. 1. The triplets for relative weightage of quality attributes (QRel) were also calculated from the calculated values of triplets for quality attributes of the samples in general. The ‘Relative weightage of the quality attribute’ for color, flavor, taste and mouthfeel were defined as: QCrel = QC/ Qsum, flavor: QFrel = QF/ Qsum, taste: QTrel = QT/Qsum and for mouthfeel: QMrel = QM/ Qsum, where Qsum is the sum of first digit of triplets of all quality attributes in general.

Triplets for overall sensory scores of the samples

The triplets for overall sensory scores of snack food samples were calculated using eq.2, in which triplet for sensory score for each quality attribute was multiplied with the triplet for relative weightage of that particular attribute and the sum of resultant triplet values for all attributes was taken.

$$S01 = CS1 \times QC_{rel} + FS1 \times QF_{rel} + TS1 \times QT_{rel} + MS1 \times QM_{rel} \dots 2$$

Where CS1, FS1, TS1, and MS1 signify the triplets corresponding to the colour, flavor, taste and mouthfeel of sample while QCrel, QFrel, QTrel, and QMrel denote the triplets corresponding to the relative weightages of quality attributes the sticks and market sample in general. The overall sensory scores for all samples were calculated using similar equation. The multiplication of triplet (a b c) with triplet (d e f) was done by applying a rule as given in Eq. 3.

$$(a \ b \ c) \times (d \ e \ f) = (a \times d \ a \times e + d \times b \ a \times f + d \times c) \dots 3$$

Membership function for standard fuzzy scale

The triplets obtained by Five Point scale are converted into Six Point sensory scale referred to as Standard Fuzzy scale. The triangular distribution pattern of sensory scales using symbols F1, F2, F3, F4, F5 and F6 is given in Figure 2. Membership function of each of the sensory scales follows triangular distribution pattern where maximum value of membership function is one. The values of fuzzy membership function lie between 0 and 1. Therefore, values of F1 through F6 are defined by a set of 10 numbers as given in Eq. 4.

$$F1 = (1, 0.5, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0)$$

$$F2 = (0.5, 1, 1, 0.5, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0)$$

$$F3 = (0, 0, 0.5, 1, 1, 0.5, 0, 0, 0, 0)$$

$$F4 = (0, 0, 0, 0, 0.5, 1, 1, 0.5, 0, 0)$$

$$F5 = (0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0.5, 1, 1, 0.5)$$

$$F6 = (0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0.5, 1) \dots 4$$

Overall membership function of sensory scores on standard fuzzy scale

Overall membership function is assigned as B1, B2, B3, B4 and B5, for the overall quality triplet of all the five samples; SO1, SO2, SO3, SO4 and SO5 respectively. The overall quality, as expressed by a triplet (a, b, c) was represented by a triangle ABC, shown in Fig. 3. The figure indicates that for a triplet (a, b, c), the value of the membership function is 1 when the abscissa is a, and 0 when it is less than a-b or larger than a+c. In mathematical form the value of the membership function Bx for a given value of x on the abscissa can be represented by similar triangles as shown in eq. 5.

$$B_x = \frac{x-(a-b)}{b}$$

distribution pattern of five-point sensory scale is poor/not at all important, fair/somewhat important, medium/important, good/highly important and excellent/extremely important as shown in the Figure. Triangle “abc” on five-point scale represents membership function for poor/not at all important category, triangle “ade” represents distribution function for fair/somewhat important category, etc. Table 1 shows ‘triplets’ associated with five-point sensory scales. Here the first number of the triplet denotes coordinate of the abscissa at which value of membership function is 1. The distance between the first number and the point where the membership function is 0 on the left-hand side of the first number is denoted by the second number of the triplet. Similarly, the distance to the right of the first number where the membership function is zero is assigned as the third number of the triplet (Routray and Mishra, 2011). The sum of sensory scores, triplets associated with five-point sensory scale and the numbers of judges were used to obtain the triplet for a particular quality attribute of given sample.

For example, when total number of judges were 20 and out of the total 20 judges, four judges gave “Fair” score, six judges gave the score as “Medium”, eight gave “Good” and two gave “Excellent” for the colour attribute of a sample, the triplets for the sensory scores of colour can be calculated by Eq. 1.

$$B_x = \frac{(a+c)-x}{c}$$

for $(a-b) < x < a$

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for $a < x < (a + c)$

Where $B_x = 0$ $x < (a - b)$ and $x > (a + c)$

The ten numbers of B are (maximum value of Bx at $0 < x < 10$), (maximum value of Bx at $10 < x < 20$), (maximum value of Bx at $20 < x < 30$), (maximum value of Bx at $30 < x < 40$), (maximum value of Bx at $40 < x < 50$), (maximum value of Bx at $50 < x < 60$), (maximum value of Bx at $60 < x < 70$), (maximum value of Bx at $70 < x < 80$), (maximum value of Bx at $80 < x < 90$), (maximum value of Bx at $90 < x < 100$). Thus, for each of the five samples, the value of membership function Bx for x values 0 – 10, 10 – 20, 20 – 30, 30 – 40, 40 – 50, 50 – 60, 60 – 70, 70 – 80, 80 – 90, and 90 – 100 can be found out from Eq. 5.

Similarity values and ranking of the samples

After getting the B values for each of the samples on standard fuzzy scale as a set of 10 values, the levels of similarity values for each sample were obtained by the equation 6 (Sinija and Mishra, 2011).

$$S_m(F, B) = \frac{1}{\text{Max}(F \times F' \text{ and } B \times B')} \quad \dots 6$$

Where S_m is the sample's similarity value, $F \times B'$ is the product of matrix F and transpose of matrix B', $F \times F'$ is the product of matrix F and the transpose of F, and $B \times B'$ is the product of matrix B and its transpose. $S_m(F_1, B_1)$, $S_m(F_2, B_1)$, $S_m(F_3, B_1)$, $S_m(F_4, B_1)$, $S_m(F_5, B_1)$ and $S_m(F_6, B_1)$ will be the similarity values for sample one (F6, B1). The values were calculated using the rules of matrix multiplication.

The maximum similarity value was determined by comparing similarity values from across six sensory scale categories. The category with the highest similarity value was considered responsible for the product's quality. Using the procedure outlined above, the overall quality of each sample was calculated. Fuzzy comprehensive modelling was used to rank three samples and quality attributes in general by combining the defined and calculated overall qualities of the samples (Zhang and Litchfield, 1991).

Results and Discussion

The sensory scores for three prepared samples as given by the panel of judges' is shown in Table 2. Fuzzy logic was used to analyse the sensory attributes of the samples (Das, 2005).

Triplets for sensory quality of the samples

The sum of sensory scores according to preferences given by the judges for the samples prepared from the pearl millet sticks with onion slices (S1), pearl millet sticks (S2) and market sample (S3) are given in Table 2. Triplets, which are sets of three numbers, were used to create triangular membership function distributions of sensory scales.

Calculation of sensory quality attributes of the samples in triplets form (Column 7 of Table 2) was done from (i) sum of sensory scores given by judges during sensory evaluation, (ii) triplets associated with the sensory scale (Table 1) and (iii) number of judges who gave tick mark under particular head on sensory scale (Table 2). The sum of sensory scores, triplets associated with a five-point sensory scale, and the numbers of judges were used to calculate the triplet for a specific quality attribute of a given sample. The results of calculations of triplets for three samples under sensory evaluation are given in Table 2.

Triplets for importance of quality attributes in general and relative weightage

The sensory scores given by judges and the triplets for quality attributes in general of the samples are given in Table 3. The triplets for individual preference to the importance of quality attributes of the samples in general were calculated using the eq. 1 similar to triplets for three samples. As a result, the triplets for judges' preference for quality attributes, namely colour (QC), flavour (QF), taste (QT), and mouthfeel (QM), were as shown in Table 3 and were indicated as eq. 7.

The value of the first digit of the overall sensory score must be between 0 and 100. To do this, the values of triplets for quality characteristics in Table 3 were reduced by a factor $1/Q_{\text{sum}}$, where Q_{sum} is the sum of the first digits of all the triplets computed as shown in eq. 8 (Singh *et al.*, 2012).

$$Q_{\text{sum}} = 65.00 + 65.00 + 82.50 + 95.00 = 307.5 \quad \dots 7$$

The values for the relative weightage of the qualitative attributes for colour, flavour, taste, and mouthfeel were computed as follows:

$$QC_{\text{rel}} = (0.2114 \quad 0.0813 \quad 0.0691)$$

$$QF_{\text{rel}} = (0.2114 \quad 0.1057 \quad 0.1057)$$

$$QT_{\text{rel}} = (0.2683 \quad 0.0813 \quad 0.0488)$$

$$QM_{\text{rel}} = (0.3090 \quad 0.0813 \quad 0.0162) \quad \dots 8$$

Overall sensory scores as triplets for the samples

The sum of the products of the triplets for the samples (Table 2) and relative weightages (eq. 8) using eq. (2) and the triplet multiplication procedure given in eq. 8 produced the overall sensory scores triplets for the samples. The following are the computed triplet values for total sensory scores of Sample 1 (SOS1), Sample 2 (SOS2), and Sample 3 (SOS3) as shown in eq. 9.

$$SOS_1 = (77.74 \quad 52.96 \quad 28.40)$$

$$SOS_2 = (83.28 \quad 51.45 \quad 24.56)$$

$$SOS_3 = (29.90 \quad 27.86 \quad 29.87) \quad \dots 9$$

From the first digit values in triplets for three samples, it can be inferred that people have preferred sample 2 which is pearl millet stick.

Membership function of overall sensory scores on standard fuzzy scale

Overall membership functions for triplets of Sample 1, Sample 2 and Sample 3 on standard fuzzy scale were calculated by using the eq. 5 and values in eq. 9. These values (B1 to B10) are called as fuzzy membership values and are given in eq. 10 as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 BS1 &= (0 \quad 0 \quad 0.1827 \quad 0.3716 \quad 0.5604 \quad 0.7492 \quad 1 \quad 0.8561 \quad 0.7631 \quad 0.4115) \\
 BS2 &= (0 \quad 0 \quad 0.0721 \quad 0.2664 \quad 0.4608 \quad 0.6551 \quad 1 \quad 0.9745 \quad 0.907 \quad 0.4990) \\
 BS3 &= (0 \quad 0.2857 \quad 0.6440 \quad 1 \quad 0.662 \quad 0.3271 \quad 0 \quad 0 \quad 0 \quad 0) \quad \dots 10
 \end{aligned}$$

Similarity values and ranking of the samples

The similarity values were calculated by comparing the membership function values (BS1, BS2, BS3) of three samples in eq. 10 with their corresponding F1 to F6 values in eq. 4.

Table 1. Triplets associated with five-point sensory scale

Poor/Not at all important	Fair/Somewhat important	Good/ Important	Very good/Highly important	Excellent/extremely important
0 0 25	25 25 25	50 25 25	75 25 25	100 25 0

Table 2. Sum of sensory scores in terms of preference given by judges and corresponding triplets for sensory quality of the samples

Sensory quality attributes	Poor	Fair	Medium	Good	Excellent	Triplets for sensory scores
Colour						
Sample 1	1	0	2	9	8	CS ₁ = (78.75 23.75 15.00)
Sample 2	0	0	3	6	11	CS ₂ = (36.75 25.00 11.25)
Sample 3	10	7	3	0	0	CS ₃ = (16.25 12.50 25.00)
Flavour						
Sample 1	0	1	2	12	9	FS ₁ = (81.25 25.00 13.75)
Sample 2	0	0	1	8	7	FS ₂ = (82.50 25.00 16.25)
Sample 3	4	9	5	2	0	FS ₃ = (31.25 20.00 25.00)
Taste						
Sample 1	1	0	1	5	13	TS ₁ = (86.25 23.75 08.75)
Sample 2	0	0	1	9	10	TS ₂ = (86.25 25.00 12.50)
Sample 3	2	5	10	2	1	TS ₃ = (43.50 22.50 23.75)
Mouthfeel						
Sample 1	1	0	2	5	12	MS ₁ = (83.75 23.75 10.00)
Sample 2	8	0	1	2	17	MS ₂ = (95.00 25.00 03.75)
Sample 3	0	7	2	2	1	MS ₃ = (23.25 15.00 23.75)

Table 3. Sum of sensory scores in terms of preferences given by judges and triplets for Importance of quality attributes of the samples in general

Quality attributes	NI	SI	I	HI	EI	Triplets for sensory score	Triplets for relative weightages
Colour	0	0	11	6	3	C = (65.00 25.00 21.25)	(0.211 0.081 0.069)
Flavour	0	2	6	10	2	F = (65.00 32.50 32.50)	(0.211 0.105 0.105)
Taste	0	0	2	10	8	T = (82.50 25.00 15.00)	(0.268 0.081 0.048)
Mouthfeel	0	0	0	4	16	M = (95.00 25.00 5.00)	(0.309 0.081 0.016)

NI – Not at all important, SI – Somewhat important, I – Important, HI – Highly important, EI – Extremely important

Table 4. Similarity values of the samples and their ranking

Sensory scale	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3
Poor	0	0	0.6999
Fair	0.0894	0.0504	0.5718
Medium	0.3392	0.2680	0.8590
Good	0.6319	0.6023	0.2632
Very good	0.6355	0.6850	0
Excellent	0.1924	0.2340	0
Ranking	II	I	III

Table 5. Similarity values of quality attributes of the samples in general

Scale factors	Colour	Flavour	Taste	Mouthfeel (Texture)
Not at all important	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000

Somewhat important	0.0000	0.0369	0.0000	0.0000
Important	0.3200	0.3823	0.0200	0.0000
Very important	0.9529	0.8140	0.4200	0.0000
Highly important	0.6235	0.6413	0.8600	0.2000
Extremely important	0.0595	0.1603	0.2000	0.8000
Ranking	III	IV	II	I

Figure 1. Triplets associated with five-point sensory scale

Figure 2. Standard fuzzy scale

Figure 3. Graphical view of overall sensory score as triangle 'ABC' and triplet (a, b, c)

The samples were ranked according to their similarity values in the categories of Poor (F1), Fair (F2), Medium (F3), Good (F4), Very Good (F5), and Excellent (F6). Table 4 shows the similarity values for all three samples under different scale factors. The maximum similarity value for Sample 2 is in the category of 'very good,' (0.6850) as shown in Table 4. Sample 1 has maximum similarity value is in category of 'very good' (0.6355) which is very near to sample 2. While sample 3 had maximum similarity value in category of 'medium' (0.8590). On comparison of highest similarity values, their ranking was done as Sample 2 (Very good) > Sample 1 (Very good) > Sample 3 (Medium), where Sample 1 is prepared product with onion slices, Sample 2 is prepared product and Sample 3 is market sample. Thus, results indicated that pearl millet sticks sample was preferred by the judges. The close tie between sample 2 and sample 1 under very good category indicated that the addition of onion slices has little effect on increasing the appeal to the consumer and do not add much taste and flavour to the pearl millet sticks if consumed with the dry snack food.

Fuzzy Membership function of quality attributes in general on standard fuzzy scale

Quality attributes (colour, flavor, taste and mouthfeel) of the sticks and market sample in general were calculated and ranked by adopting similar procedure. The triplets for importance of these quality attributes in general have been given in Table 3. Using the above method of computation and denoting BC, BF, BT and BM as overall sensory scores on standard fuzzy scale for membership function of colour, flavor, taste and mouthfeel respectively, we get BC = (0 0 0 0.4 0.8 1 0.7647 0.2941 0)

BF = (0 0 0 0.2307 0.5384 0.8461 1 0.08461 0.5384 0.2307)

BT= (0 0 0 0 0 0.1 0.5 0.9 1 0)

BM= (0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 1)

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The similarity values of four quality attributes of the the sticks and market sample werecalculated by eq. 6 using the F values in eq. 4 and B values in eq. 11. The computed values are given in Table 5. These values in show that mouthfeel (0.8000) is the highest quality characteristic in the scale factor of 'Extremely important', followed by taste (0.8600) in the scale factor of 'Highly important', colour (0.9529) in the scale factor of 'very important' and flavour (0.8140) in the scale factor of 'very important'. The order of choice for quality attributes for the samples in general was Mouthfeel (Extremely important)>Taste (Highly important)>colour (very important)>flavour (very important). Mouthfeel, or texture, was the highest quality attribute for pearl millet snack food, while flavour was the weakest among thequality attributes. The close tie implies that customer preferences and products are well- established. As a result, according to the preferences of the judges in this evaluation, taste and mouthfeel are the most important quality characteristics, whereas flavour is the least importantquality attribute. It can be concluded that fuzzy logic analysis can be used for sensory evaluation of RTE dried snack foods, and these samples can be ranked according to customer choice.

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